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The Historical Evolution of Fuel Subsidy Policies in Nigeria and Their Socio-Economic Impact

KEYWORDS

fuel subsidy policies, Nigeria, socio-economic impact, historical evolution, policy abolition, renewable energy sources, energy sector reforms

ABSTRACT

Introduction. Analysis of fuel subsidy policies in Nigeria reveals their impact on the state budget and living standards of the population, and also contributes to the formation of more efficient and sustainable energy strategies.

The aim of the article: to analyze the historical stages of fuel subsidy policy in Nigeria and its socio-economic impact.

Materials and methods. The research utilized articles from peer-reviewed international journals as well as scientific collections published by Springer, covering topics related to African economic, social, and political development, among others. The methodology included an analysis of the advantages and disadvantages of subsidy policies' impact on the population of Nigeria.

Results. The abolition of fuel subsidy policies in 2023 provided long-term sustainability despite immediate policy adjustments.

It emphasizes the need for targeted investments in renewable energy sources and the improvement of policies aimed at minimizing the negative consequences of reforms in the energy sector, contributing to the achievement of sustainable development goals.

Conclusion. The historical evolution of fuel subsidy policies in Nigeria is complex and shows the interplay between economic stability, social well-being, and public interest. Currently, Nigeria pursues proper consistency and reforms to achieve a more sustainable economic model. This model involves reinvesting released resources in infrastructure development, welfare programs, and diversification for long-term economic sustainability.

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INTRODUCTION

Fuel subsidies have been part of the economy in Nigeria for decades and were introduced to make fuel more affordable for citizens and support economic stability. Over the years, the government has used subsidies to control fuel prices, ease transportation costs, and reduce inflation. The reforms have therefore brought relief to ordinary Nigerians but, at the same time, placed a heavy financial burden on the government. This has led to endless debate on whether they should be maintained or removed.

History gives a clearer view into how fuel subsidies have built up the economy of Nigeria and its societal impacts. On quite a number of occasions throughout history, government spending on fuel subsidies affected business operations, enterprises, and aspects of normal life for any Nigerian. Less often, with the reduction of fuel subsidies or actual removal, their prices go up; economic struggles become more pronounced and especially among low-income earners.

The historical discourse associated with fuel subsidies in Nigeria, their economic and social impacts, and how public opinion sentiment has changed over time are explored, to explain how the policies of fuel subsidy bring about challenges and opportunities together with its long-run effects on the economy of Nigeria.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The material for the research comprised articles from peer-reviewed international journals: «Journal of African Economies», «Transport Policy», «Journal of Development Economics», «Journal of Transportation Technologies», «Nigerian Journal of Social Sciences», «Economic Analysis», «Development Studies Quarterly», «Economic Development Quarterly», «Journal of Agricultural Economics», «The Energy Journal», and others.

Springer published collections of scientific articles, including «Advances in African Economic, Social and Political Development». Springer Proceedings in Business and Economics», among others.

Research methods included an analysis of the advantages and disadvantages of the impact of subsidy policies on the population of Nigeria.

RESULTS

Historical Background of Fuel Subsidies in Nigeria

The historical concepts associating the removal of fuel subsidies have been in several decades in Nigeria. The prices of pump changes and this hasn't been stable, rather it has a great impact on the political landscape of the country. Tracing back from 1978 during the tenure of Gen. Olusegun Obasanjo, the price of pump for fuel was high from 8.4 kobo to 15.37 kobo, marks 83% increase. The said increment was to augment the government's revenue in the run-up to the 1979 democratic dispensation and service the people's increasingly dire socio-economic needs. The governments of Alhaji Shehu Shagari equally continued from January 1982, and by then, fuel prices further escalated from 15.37 kobo to 20 kobo, that is a jump by 30% to the new rates.

But the funds that were gotten from the increase of the fuel wasn't for the public welfare rather it was for personal gains, so all these then led to the fall of the regime. The era of General Babangida saw further increase in fuel prices with the pump prices going up from 39.50 kobo to 60 kobo in March 1986 including 98% increase. Implementation of the Structural Adjustment Programme (SAP) also uses such factors as economic crises, unrest across the country against the policies of the government. Although in the 1990s, there are successive administrations that were associated with challenges posed by fuel subsidy removal, between price increases and the reductions in the public outcry response. Despite these adjustments program, fuel prices had continued to rise steadily, with significant hikes during the second term as civilian president of Olusegun Obasanjo. The years leading to 2012 were defined by tension over fuel subsidy removal, as the administration led by President Goodluck Jonathan was in the eye of the hurricane of a virulent outcry from the public over the announcement of the elimination of fuel subsidies.

The decision, which was announced by the Petroleum Product Pricing Regulatory Agency on January 1st, 2012, elicited a nationwide protest and strikes accompanied it; thus making the government bring back and then partially implement subsidy reduction.

The fuel subsidy had become an intensive financial burden on Nigeria, amounting to almost \$8 billion and indicating even higher costs in 2012. Furthermore, the severe effects of the subsidy on the market continue to bring huge losses. While the short-term political challenges of its removal are well known, transparent and well-designed reforms could redirect the substantial funds allocated to the fuel

subsidy program toward more impactful uses. More than this, Nigeria ranks among the countries that are globally leading in terms of oil production, with an aggregate proven reserve of 37.2 billion barrels. In spite of these facts, wealth gotten from the mineral resources does not seem to translate into greater improvements in ways of living by the people. Surprisingly, more than a quarter of Nigeria's citizens account for 54 percent, that continue to live below the country minimum level known as poverty [1]. Garba identifies that the discontinuation of subsidies continues to be an often and widely argued subject in Nigeria [2]. Although full removal hasn't happened since 2016, successive administrations have reflected on subsidy revisions and any other means to tackle the fiscal difficulties surrounded with the subsidy framework. The Federal Government, decided to use fiscal pressures by with the announcement of the absence of fuel subsidies, then it results in a great price increase from N86 to N145 per litre, representing an 80% increase.

The step allows the government to take action against fiscal imbalances and work toward economic sustainability. At the cost of public outcry and socio-political unrest. In a bold move, the newly inaugurated administration, under the leadership of President Bola Ahmed Tinubu, brought a rather sharp approach to the matter when he announced the cessation of fuel subsidies in his inaugural speech at Eagle Square. He said, "Fuel subsidies are now a thing of the past! The rising costs of subsidies can no longer be justified given the diminishing availability of resources". Fuel pump prices were, therefore, immediately adjusted to N540 per litre. The price of fuel in Nigeria, as at March 2023, is between 617 and 670 Naira per liter, although it may slightly differ from one filling station to another, with possibilities of further increases. Initial tensions were that potential strike actions were averted following extensive dialogue between the government and labour unions. The removal of petrol subsidies in Nigeria is a sensitive issue and highly controversial topic, with implications for the economy, society, politics, public views, global oil prices, and the government's financial status – all come into play in this discussion.

Economic Consequences of Subsidy Policies

Adenikinju and Alimi conducted a research that examines the effects of removing fuel subsidies that bring about inflation rates in Nigeria [3]. Their findings show that subsidies elimination can be caused by high inflation rates that can also be linked with the increase in transportation costs and expenses in production. Other authors know as Oluwatosin and Oluwatosin gave the deep impacts of the removal of

subsidy on transportation costs in Nigeria [4]. This indicated the discontinuation of fuel subsidies led to a very high increase in transportation cost nationwide, as lots of expenses were involved. This increase was viewed higher due to fuel prices having a straight impact on the cost of transporting goods and services. Olawale and Adeola opinion was on the living activities of Nigerians expenses that include subsidy removal [5]. It indicates that through the research, there is an identification that the removal of subsidies led to high household living activities with expenses due to the higher prices for essential goods and services. This has increased the cost of living and has maintained more financial stress on households, especially those having sources of income that are on lower levels. Furthermore, various studies have looked deeply into the macro-economic effects of the removal of subsidy on the growth of Gross Domestic Product, household welfare, which is important, and sectors performance in Nigeria. Adenikinju and Alimi proffered an idea that sought to measure the impact of subsidy removal on GDP growth, noting a kind of temporary slow-down that businesses had experienced as adjustment was made for the higher production cost [6]. This notwithstanding, observe a gradual recovery in GDP growth as the economy adjusted itself to the new pricing regime. Oluwatosin and Oluwatosin analyzed the impact of the removal of subsidies on household welfare in Nigeria. Their findings reveal that poor households were equally affected by the removal of the subsidies, hence their purchasing effort and welfare declined. Olowale and Adeola gave an analysis on the sectors' performance following subsidy removal. The observation has gotten what is seen as mixed outcomes across different sectors. While some of the industries were facing challenges in relation to the increase in operation costs, others benefitted from it, especially the creation of a more level playing field where the market wasn't distorted by subsidies.

Impact on Economic Sectors

The impacts of fuel subsidies policies on the Nigerian economy are being studied with diverse methods and tools of analysis that offer great insight into the various impacts of this policy change.

Fuel subsidy removal is really an issue with implications for a stable economy, welfare of people, and changes in politics. Adekunle and Adeoye gave out the result of fuel subsidy removal in January 2012 on the Nigerian economy. With the use of a vector error correction model (VECM), it resulted in an essential positive impact on GDP growth post-removal. However, the study also identifies an intense

effect on inflation associated with the increase in fuel prices. Moreso, Olawuyi and Ajayi were specific on the transportation sector showing the repercussions of fuel subsidy removal within this aspect [7]. They used regression analysis to uncover the increase in transportation costs of post-removal. Hence, the influences experienced in the price changes of goods and services also include a negative influence in the growth of the sectors since the sectors are vulnerable to policy changes.

Then again, in 2015, Adeleke and Adekunle contributed to the opinion of the agricultural sector by analyzing the impacts of fuel subsidy reforms on the products in agriculture [8]. From the panel data regression analysis aimed at obtaining the most reduction path in the growth of the sector post-removal, it was largely attributed to an increase in the costs of production following a hike in fuel prices to challenge farmers and businesses associated with agriculture.

Oyetale and Ojo employed panel data regression analysis to investigate the impact of fuel subsidy removal on the manufacturing sector in Nigeria and found a negative consequence on its growth after the removal. Additionally, their study showed that the production cost increased with an effect on competitiveness and viability of the sectors concerned.

It demonstrates an understanding of the impacts of fuel subsidy reforms on various sectors of the Nigerian economy with emphasis on the various changes at play, which offer ideas for policymakers, economists, and stakeholders. The issue led to further research and analysis to form evidence-based policy solutions that would promote stable economic welfare of the people and sustainable development in Nigeria.

Influence of Fuel Subsidy Removal on Various Sectors in Nigeria

Figure 1 Economic impacts

It shows that the subsidy reforms brings an increase in the transportation cost than other sectors.

Social Implications and Policy Evaluation and Reform

The Omotola study of 2016 relates to the social impact of fuel subsidy in Nigeria [9]. It concerns public attitudes towards, and their reactions in relation to, modification of the policy, so exposing possibilities of social disagreements and political backlash that result from cessation of the fuel subsidy. Adeleke and Olaniyan took a deeper look at the issue of public opinion on fuel subsidy removal in Nigeria, looking through how different groups or parts of the society interpreted the decision of the government and its effects on social unity and stability in politics [10]. Their research gave the dimensional opinion that is dominant in the Nigerian society regarding the shifts in policy. Ibrahim and Bello assessed the sentiment was more among the public associating fuel subsidy removal in Nigeria with cuts across to social implications on various parts of the society and tendencies experiencing social unrest or not being stable politically [11]. The results offer some insight important in the perceptions and responses of the Nigerian population toward the discontinuation of fuel subsidies. The various studies conducted in Nigeria shed light on the authors' in-depth view into the frameworks and methods used in assessing the effectiveness of subsidy removal policies through evaluation and reform.

Bamidele and Saibu evaluated the impact of fuel subsidy removal on the growth of the economy [12]. It uses econometric techniques for the analysis of data and this shows that subsidy removal at the beginning led to inflation that is surrounded with pressures, although the contribution was based on the long-term stability of a stable economy by redirecting resources to sectors that are productive. Adenikinju looked into the challenges and opportunities like benefits associated with the programs of subsidy reforms [13]. Adenikinju identifies challenges arising from subsidy policies that implicate transparency, governance, and political economy considerations. There is, therefore, a heightened call to understand reform strategies that will address these challenges while being dependent on opportunities to enhance efficiency and fiscal sustainability. Moreover, Jerome examined the implication surrounding the subsidy reforms on long-term sustainability of the economy that explains the importance of phasing out subsidies gradually to reduce intense effects on vulnerable populations and ensure smooth changes to price methods of the market [14]. It also examined the possible gain of reforms subsidy programs in terms of fiscal stress reduction,

investment in the private sector promotion as well as competition increase in the economy. Furthermore, Ogundipe, Adebayo, & Ogundipe used survey method to examine the impacts of fuel subsidies removal on the well-being of a household [15].

It depicts that the removal of fuel subsidies commenced with the price hike and a decline in the welfare of the household, where the economy produces long-term advantages. Moreso, Ogundipe & Alimi research was centered on the political economic aspects of fuel subsidy removal in Nigeria [16]. This solution looked into that is associated with implementing such a policy change within a country that has depended on subsidy in the past. This underlined the necessity of involving stakeholders in the process, showing transparency, and ensuring proper communication for any successful effort in policy reform. In addition, Aigheyisi gave the opinion of implications of subsidy reforms on the productivity in agriculture [17]. The study targeted the support and methods for the reduction of potential negative impacts of subsidy removals on the vulnerable sectors such as agriculture. The outcomes of various subsidy programs on the performance of agriculture provided an understanding of great value to policymakers that seeks to enhance long-term economic sustainability. Among the challenges and opportunities associated with subsidy program reforms, one of the major challenges manifested by Ogundipe & Alimi was resistance from vested interests benefiting from the existing subsidy reforms.

For such resistance to be surmounted, there are prerequisites in the form of strategic plans, coalition building, and effective communication in order to aim support for reform initiatives.

Figure 2 The graphs explain trends on the fiscal impact of the government budget

On the other hand, Aigheyisi noted that subsidy reforms would offer the prospect of giving resources to more productive sectors and hence enhance efficiency in the economy. This would allow policymakers to bring out innovation and competitiveness in key industries by redirecting funds from inefficient subsidies to specific programs focusing on promoting growth and development.

The results explain with the elimination of fuel subsidy policies in 2023 there is a long term sustainability despite the adjustments of the policies was done immediately.

Table 1

Analytical Achievement: Effects of Subsidy policies on the People

Effects	Advantages	Disadvantages
Significant price increases	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Affordable for urban dwellers due to their high income - In the study, gave the opinion that not all classes are affected by prices of commodities, the bourgeois will always remain at the helm of the upper class 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Rural population earns low, and they are affected by the increase of commodities - The study in shows financial strain on citizens, difficulties encountered in accessing commodities
Challenges faced by the people due to lackof adequate preparation and planning of the reform	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - It helped reduce government spending and promote market-driven pricing mechanisms - The expert used in the study gave the opinion on the potential Increased of government revenue from reduce of subsidy expenditure 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - In contrast, it led to higher fuel prices for consumers, potentially causing inflationary pressures and impacting lower-income households disproportionately - Furthermore, the hindered execution of planned projects due to increased financial burden
Low-income earners and businesses	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Government's cash transfer program helped alleviate the living expenses for low-income household - The study, highlight the Increased of salaries would potentially reduce the shock gotten from the reform 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The unveiling widespread protests and social unrest among lower-income groups heavily reliant on subsidized fuel - Closure of small businesses and increased financial hardship for low-income families
Transportation influences	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - More resources are given efficiently in transportation sector to assist the individuals - Potential for improved public transportation infrastructure 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The repercussions of fuel subsidy removal on transportation costs. They discovered a substantial uptick in transportation expenses - The study identifies the tripling of travel costs and hindered growth for businesses
Impact on manufacturing, agricultural produce, and other sectors	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The urban residents have accessibility of these sectors due to their high disposable income - In the study, the reform has introduced palliative measures and support for the affected sectors 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - In contrast, rural populations relied heavily on subsidized fuels for agriculture and transportation purposes, making any potential increase in fuel prices a significant concern for them - Fishing and agricultural activities has increased in the south regions

Government budget and expenditure priorities	- The study shows the adjustment of government budget to support affected sectors	- Risk of increased public debt - Stress on government resources and doubts about effective resource allocation
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Reducing Subsidies and Further Developing Renewable Energy Sources in Nigeria

F. B. Dayo and A. O. Adegbulugbe note that oil, first discovered in Nigeria in 1956 by the Shell-BP Development Company, contributed significantly to the country's economic development. The exploitation of this resource enabled Nigeria to transition from a chronic trade deficit to a substantial surplus. However, by the end of 1977, the country again registered a deficit in visible trade [18; 19].

J. S. Ovadia argues that five decades of oil production in Nigeria have not yielded meaningful economic or social development. The author posits that the "Nigerian content" policy is a project designed to secure greater benefits from the nation's oil wealth for the domestic elite [20].

A. O. Akinola and H. Wissink attribute the crisis in the Nigerian oil industry, which led to subsidy reductions and attempts to deregulate the refining sector, to the poor performance of the country's public sector in managing these issues [21].

According to J. Rentschler and M. Bazilian, subsidy reforms should extend beyond providing fiscal relief to also contribute to achieving long-term sustainable development goals. The scholars emphasize that implementing such reforms necessitates intertwining environmental objectives with fiscal, macroeconomic, political, and social considerations [22].

M. Jakob et al. contend that reforming fossil fuel subsidies could free up sufficient funds to finance universal access to water, sanitation, and electricity in many countries, while also aiding in the reduction of global greenhouse gas emissions [23].

A. E. Ezeoha and C. Uche argue that the challenges in reforming gasoline subsidies in a country like Nigeria stem more from a pronounced lack of state legitimacy and public trust, coupled with instances of political instability exacerbated by coercive reform attempts. The researchers posit that the Nigerian case illustrates a fundamental shift from traditional to a more functional context in citizens' perception of governance as a source of legitimacy [24].

In May 2023, Nigerian President Bola Tinubu officially terminated the long-standing gasoline subsidy. Public opinion was markedly ambivalent, combining discontent

and apprehension with a recognition of the reform's necessity for the country. O. Adebomi analyzes internet memes related to President Tinubu's fuel subsidy abolition policy to identify how Nigerians critique and digitally resist what they perceive as an anti-populist measure. The study finds that Nigerians utilize memes to negatively portray the Tinubu administration and expose the purported anti-people ideology underlying the subsidy removal [25].

E. Igwebuike et al. conduct a pragma-semiotic analysis of online publications by the Occupy Nigeria Group concerning the 2012 fuel subsidy removal, examining verbal and visual methods of representing actors and their actions. The authors note that the verbal mode complements the visual in projecting the group's demands and resistance [26].

G. Bamgbose reveals that the use of memes constitutes genuine socio-political commentary and simultaneously functions as a coping mechanism for citizens grappling with socio-political challenges [27].

The transition to renewable energy in Nigeria is crucial for enhancing energy security, reducing greenhouse gas emissions, expanding electricity access, and stimulating economic development, all while fulfilling international climate commitments. Despite growing calls for reform, numerous countries continue to maintain subsidies for gasoline and diesel.

According to L. W. Davis, these subsidies result in USD 44 billion in external costs annually [28]. P. Mahdavi et al. note that while many governments have pledged to reduce fossil fuel subsidies, researchers question the effectiveness of the strategies employed to achieve these cuts [29].

S. Diallo et al. argue that governmental focus on subsidizing fossil fuels disadvantages renewable energy sources and may impede the energy transition in the region. The authors conclude that increased subsidies are decelerating the shift to cleaner energy [30].

A. Isah et al. identify policy uncertainty and weak financing mechanisms as key impediments to renewable energy investment in Nigeria. The scholars conclude that Nigeria requires a robust policy framework, a dynamic public development bank, strategic use of blended finance, and diversification of financial instruments to accelerate investment in renewables [31].

C. Okereke et al. highlight that limited energy access remains one of Nigeria's most pressing development challenges. According to their projections, Nigeria's

power generation capacity could rise to 398 GW, 250 GW, and 347 GW by 2060 under Current Policy (CPS), Green Energy Shift (GES), and Renewable Energy Shift (RES) scenarios, respectively. The analysis suggests a potential pathway for Nigeria to meet its commitments for universal energy access while decarbonizing the electricity sector to align with net-zero emission targets [32].

F. Abam et al. predict a 61-67% improvement in carbon intensity by 2030. The researchers underscore the necessity for coordinated policies on energy efficiency, fossil fuel phase-out, renewable energy integration, and behavioral change to achieve a transition to a low-carbon economy within Nigeria's housing sector [33].

In 2023, the Nigerian leadership announced the removal of gasoline subsidies, marking the beginning of an era of phasing out all forms of fuel subsidies in the country.

N. S. Balke et al. found that subsidy removal would reduce the global oil price by six percent. The removal of subsidies unequivocally enhances the welfare of oil-importing countries. Subsidy removal also increases the welfare of oil-exporting countries in the baseline calibration [34].

S. N. Okoroafor et al. examine the implications of fuel subsidy removal by analyzing the complex and multifaceted interplay of economic, political, environmental, and social factors. The authors demonstrate the negative impact of removing fuel subsidies on households and businesses in terms of income, welfare, and poverty indicators [35].

I. O. Ogundari et al. show that past reductions in fuel subsidies – typically leading to higher fuel prices – were actually accompanied by an increase in demand for gasoline and diesel and a decrease in demand for kerosene. The decline in kerosene demand will have significant environmental consequences, as rural dwellers and the urban poor will be forced to meet their energy needs through alternative means [36].

K. B. Ajeigbe investigated the relationship between fuel subsidies and sustainable development goals in selected African countries for the period 2010–2022. The researchers contend that in the event of subsidy removal, the saved funds must be channeled into development projects and renewable energy sources, which can stimulate the economy and reduce poverty [37].

C. Liu and Y. Xu argue that subsidies lead to the overconsumption of fossil fuels, resulting in resource wastage, increased fiscal burdens on governments, cross-border smuggling of fossil fuels, inequitable distribution between wealthy and poor residents, increased carbon dioxide emissions, and hindrance to the utilization and development of clean energy [38].

O. J. Olujobi and O. S. Irumekhai uncover the complexities associated with gasoline subsidy payments, which lead to corruption, rent-seeking behavior, and the underutilization of clean energy sources. According to the researchers, a significant gap exists in Nigeria's energy sector compared to selected participant countries in the study [39].

N. Droste et al. believe that fossil fuel subsidies remain a significant obstacle to achieving the goals of the Paris Agreement. The authors suggest that supporting renewable energy could serve as a leverage point for overcoming carbon lock-in in fossil fuel-based economies [40].

M. Mbamalu argues that renewable energy in Nigeria has suffered for decades from negative public perception and insufficient understanding [41]. A number of authors explore issues related to the development of other energy sources, particularly biofuel (cassava) [42], water [43] etc.

H. N. Wali et al. investigate the prospects for adopting solar energy systems in urban areas of Kano State, Nigeria. According to the authors, 31.25% of households have adopted solar energy. Subsidizing the production of materials for solar energy would reduce installation costs, enabling low-income groups to afford solar energy adoption [44].

A. R. Ejiogu points out that gas flaring from oil production has a significant environmental, health, and financial impact on the country. The author highlights the associated environmental and health issues, legal and socio-economic concerns, and provides policy recommendations for ending gas flaring in Nigeria [45].

I. Emohefe Odenu writes that in Delta State (Nigeria), households use environmentally unsustainable energy sources such as firewood, charcoal, and kerosene for cooking. These unsustainable energy sources pose significant health and environmental risks, including respiratory diseases, greenhouse gas emissions, air pollution, harmful pollutants, and even fatalities [46].

Analysis of the scientific literature shows that the reduction of subsidies contributes to a decrease in global oil prices, which potentially increases the welfare of importing countries, and also fosters the development of renewable energy sources. Overall, the results underscore the necessity of targeted investments in renewable energy and the refinement of policies aimed at minimizing the negative consequences of energy sector reforms, thereby facilitating the achievement of sustainable development goals.

CONCLUSION

The historical evolution of fuel subsidy policies in Nigeria is intricate, showing interactions between economic stability, social welfare and public interest. Originally enacted to cushion the population from fuel price volatility, long-term effects of subsidies include financial strain on the government, corruption, and inefficient resource allocation. Successive administrations have been challenged by the huge task of subsidy reforms in view of vehement public opposition to such changes and the economic hardships facing citizens.

The economic and social implications of subsidy removal range from impacts on inflation to the cost of transportation and the welfare of households. Now, proper sequencing and reforms help nudge Nigeria toward a more sustainable economic model in which freed resources are reinvested into infrastructure development, public welfare programs, and diversification for long-run economic resilience.

However, subsidy removal is such a controversial issue hence the strategic, transparent and inclusive approach shall be very imperative to balance economic growth with social equity.

The following are the policy recommendations proposed in addressing the historical and continuing challenges associated with fuel subsidies in Nigeria:

1. The need for transparency in fiscal management and policy implementation: Increased transparency in fiscal decision-making and policy implementation to gain public trust and accountability. Engage the people who are going to be severely affected in the making of a decision and for them to participate in the policy basis for well-formed policies.
2. Direct funds transfer: There is a need to institute targeted social programs that will insulate low-income households from the burden that attends fuel price hikes. The mitigation measures must result in conditional cash transfer programs and subsidies of basic commodities.
3. Sudden Relief Measures and Palliative Support: This may be realized through the introduction of targeted subsidies and financial assistance for vulnerable groups and affected sectors to reduce sudden hardships. Give specific resources to support those most impacted by the subsidy removal to ensure their essential needs are met during the process.
4. Diversification of the Economy: This will reduce Nigeria's overdependence on revenues from petroleum by investing in other sectors of the economy, such

as agriculture, manufacturing, etc. The policies encouraging entrepreneurship and industrial development will help in creating more jobs and reducing the economic shock of fuel price volatilities.

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